

INDUCTION WELDING BEHAVIOR OF WOVEN-CF/PPS LAMINATES USING HIGH FREQUENCY CONTINUOUS INDUCTION HEATING

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) composites has several high performance properties such as high productivity, excellent impact resistance and recyclability compared to carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting (CFRTS) ones. Thus, CFRTP are hoping a wide range of applications in aerospace, automotive and industrial fields. However, CFRTP is manufactured at high temperature and high pressure using a commercial mold, and then an intergraded molding is undesirable for large-sized structures with complex shape. Therefore, a joining process is necessary for manufacturing of CFRTP composite structures. The joining of thermoplastic composites can be performed by several methods such as mechanical fastening, adhesive bonding and welding [2]. The mechanical fastening method has some disadvantages such as stress concentrations of hole, gain of weight and corrosion by metallic bolts and rivets. Adhesive bonding is also difficult to bond chemically between thermoplastic polymers. Therefore, the welding is suitable for CFRTP parts. There are several types of welding method for CFRTP such as ultrasonic welding, resistance welding and induction welding, but the principle of these methods is completely different. Ultrasonic welding has a size restriction of joining parts. Resistance welding has to insert a metallic heating element between joining faces generally. Moreover, it is very difficult for these methods to weld continuously between large-sized CFRTP parts with high productivity. However, the induction welding can be performed continuously by moving an induction coil with pressure roller. Though it is known that the high-frequency induction coil can vibrated directly the carbon fiber and the surrounding polymer can be heated, the mechanism of induction heating for CFRTP has not been clarified sufficiently at this moment. In this study, we clarified the effect of induction heating using an induction coil and pressurization by a pressure roller on the joints of woven-CF/PPS laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composite materials have been gaining interest as high-end applications, mainly in the aerospace field. Furthermore, in recent years, it has received great attention as an automotive and industrial application. Structures made of thermoplastic composites can be fusion bonded without using conventional joining methods; mechanical fastening and adhesive bonding. The mechanical fastening method has some disadvantages such as stress concentrations of hole, gain of weight and corrosion by metallic bolts and rivets. Adhesive bonding is also difficult to bond chemically between thermoplastic polymers. Therefore, the welding is suitable for thermoplastic composite materials parts. There are several types of welding method for thermoplastic composite materials such as ultrasonic welding, resistance welding and induction welding, and they are being studied in many research institutes. In any case, it is required to heat and fuse only the interface between joints continuously without leaving any foreign matter.

The induction welding for CFRTP can be performed continuously by moving an induction coil using a pressure roller [1]. The research on continuous induction welding of CFRTP has been clarified by many research institutes and researchers [2][3]. The applied current is operated by supplying a frequency range of several tens of kHz to several MHz to the generator. This current is applied to an

induction coil called an inductor, and as a result an alternating magnetic field is generated. Since the carbon fiber inside CFRTP have conductivity, eddy currents are applied to the carbon fiber by this alternating magnetic field. This heats the polymer inside CFRTP to a temperature that enables welding due to resistance heating, Joule heating, magnetic hysteresis loss and so on of carbon fiber [4]. In addition, in the case of woven carbon fiber, it is found that induction heating is easier than unidirectional materials because eddy currents flow through the warp and weft of carbon fiber bundles and resistance increases at the intersections of the fiber bundles [1][5][6]. Joining dissimilar materials; it is metal, glass fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) and CFRTS versus CFRTTP, has also been studied by applying these induction welding techniques [7][8][9]. However, the high frequency power supply in the hundreds of kHz bands is used in many of these researches, and there are few research cases using the high frequency power supply in the several MHz bands [10]. The authors have clarified the induction heating temperature when inductively heating woven-CF/PPS laminates using the high frequency power supply of around 2.0MHz [11]. In this study, we clarify the induction heating behavior on the fusion bond of woven-CF/PPS laminates by induction heating using the high frequency power source around 2.0MHz.

2 EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

The materials used for the induction welding experiment is 5H-sateen woven-CF/PPS laminates (TenCate, CETEX[®], $V_f=45\text{vol.}\%$) with 4 plies, $t=1.2\text{mm}$ thickness. It is shown from the result of differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) analysis that the glass-transition temperature is $T_g=90^\circ\text{C}$ and the melting temperature is $T_m=290^\circ\text{C}$. It is also shown from the result of thermogravimetric analysis (TG) that the thermal decomposition temperature is $T_d=410^\circ\text{C}$.

2.2 Determination of high frequency band

When high frequency induction heating is applied to CFRTP, the eddy current is induced in carbon fiber inside CFRTP. The inductive current occurs a direction which is at a right angle to the magnetic flux by the induction coil. This inductive current concentrates on surface of the heating object because the current is the high frequency current. This phenomenon is called the skin effect. The result of the skin effect is that most of the heat is concentrated in a specific region on the surface of heating object. This effect is decreased exponentially from the surface of heated object. The eddy current density has also decreased by $1/e$. Then, this depth is defined by the penetration depth (δ). The penetration depth is calculated by

$$\delta = 5.03 \times 10^5 \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\mu_r f}} \quad [mm] \quad (1)$$

where $\rho[\Omega \cdot \text{m}]$ is electrical resistivity, μ_r is specific magnetic permeability and f [Hz] is frequency. Then, the specific magnetic permeability is $\mu_r=1$. The penetration depth of CFRP is wide range ($\rho=0.2 \times 10^{-5} - 15 \times 10^{-5} \Omega \cdot \text{m}$) because CFRP has various fiber reinforcement morphology. The carbon fiber used for the woven-CF/PPS laminates to be heated in this study is PAN series, and the electrical resistivity in the fiber direction is $\rho=1.7 \times 10^{-5} \Omega \cdot \text{m}$. The frequency band of MHz class is considered to be suitable for heating with a thickness of several mm, so in this study we used the high frequency power supply that can be changed from 1.8 to 2.2MHz.

2.3 Selection of induction coil

It is known that the range of induction heating depends on the shape of the induction coil. In order to inductively heat the junction continuously using the induction coil as in this research, it is desirable to be able to inductively heat the joining part locally. Figure 1 shows the appearance of the double D-type coil used for magnetic flux density analysis. This double D-type coil has the outer diameter of $40 \times 50\text{mm}$ and the copper pipe diameter of 4mm. Finite element analysis (FEA) was applied using the magnetic field analysis program of ANSYS Inc. to evaluate the fabricated the double D-type induction coil. From the results of finite element analysis shown in Figure 2, it can be seen that the magnetic flux

density at the center of the double D-type induction coil is large. Therefore, local induction heating is performed continuously by moving the induction coil in the x-direction.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the induction coil geometries.

Figure 2: Finite element analysis of magnetic flux density by double D-type induction coil heating.

2.4 Induction welding method

Figure 3 shows the schematic drawing of induction welding equipment (Pearl Kogyo Co., Ltd., under development with authors) used in this study. Two plates of woven-CF/PPS laminates overlapped at the both side edges were induction heated using the double D-type coil. At this time, the joining part was pressurized while moving by the pressure roller with the optional temperature control arranged before and after the induction coil. In this study, in order to investigate the influence of the joining part, experiments were performed by changing variously the high-frequency power (P) and the air flow volume (q_a). In addition, the induction coil height (h) is 2mm, the induction coil moving speed (v) is 5mm/s, and the induction coil-pressure roller distance (d_1 , d_2) is 60mm during the experiment. When the pressure roller synchronises with an infrared thermography (Apiste Co., Ltd., FSV-1200) and induction coil at $v=5\text{mm/s}$, $d_1=60\text{mm}$, $d_2=$, the relationship of x-displacement versus process time is shown in Figure 4. During the joining process, the surface temperature (T_s) and the joining part temperature (T_i) of joining part was measured by K-type thermocouples via PEI films inserted between laminates with a data logger (Graphtech Co., Ltd., GL220). At this time, four K-type thermocouples were inserted at the positions of 120, 150, 180 and 210 mm from the left end of woven-CF/PPS laminates.

Figure 3: Schematic drawing of continuous high-frequency induction welding equipment.

Figure 4: x -displacement versus process time in moving of pressure roller.
($v=5\text{mm/s}$, $d_1=d_2=60\text{mm}$)

2.5 Evaluation method of joining part

The single lap joining (SLJ) test was carried out to evaluate a joining strength with a universal testing machine (Shimadzu Co., Ltd., AG-50kN XDplus). The cross-head speed was 0.5mm/min. The dimensions of the SLJ specimens are shown in Figure 5. Six SLJ specimens in accordance with JIS K 6850 were cut off at $w=25\text{mm}$ wide from induction-welded laminates and aluminum tabs were bonded to the both ends of specimens with epoxy adhesive. The tensile shear strength (τ_{ap}) was calculated by Eqn.2;

$$\tau_{ap} = \frac{P_{\max}}{A_L} \quad (2)$$

where P_{\max} and A_L mean maximum tensile force and overlap area, respectively.

Figure 5: The SLJ specimens in accordance with JIS K 6850.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Induction heating distribution

Figure 6 shows the heating temperature distribution of woven-CF/PPS laminates surface when high frequency induction heating is performed by changing the high-frequency power P . The dashed line on the heating temperature distribution image shows the joining part of woven-CF/PPS laminates. It was confirmed that the joint of woven-CF/PPS laminates was locally heated with the arbitrary high frequency power by the double D-type induction coil. It was found that woven-CF/PPS laminates

surface did not reach the melting point at $P=400W$, but was heated to the high temperature of $300^{\circ}C$ or more at $P=500W$ or more.

Figure 6: Temperature distribution images observed by thermography.

3.2 Induction welding behavior

Figure 7 shows the temperature change of woven-CF/PPS laminates by induction welding in constant of $P=500W$, of each K-type thermocouple. The surface temperature (T_s) and the joining part temperature (T_i) were confirmed to have the same behavior at any point measured by the thermocouple. The behavior of T_s is similar to the trend shown by R. Rudolf et al [5]. The peak temperature becomes T_m or more because woven-CF/PPS laminates is heated by high frequency induction heating. After that, solidification is started when the temperature falls below T_m . At that time, T_s is cooled down to T_g or less by the pressure roller, but it re-rises due to T_i heat conduction. On the other hand, T_i is affected by the cooling by the pressure roller, but is not quenched less than T_s . On the other hand, T_i is cooled by the pressure roller in the same manner as T_s , but not cooled below the cooling temperature of T_s . On the contrary, the heat conduction of T_i causes T_s to rise again. From these, it is important in induction welding whether only T_i can be raised without raising T_s .

Figure 7: Change of temperature for processing time of each K-type thermocouple. ($P=500W$)

Figure 8 shows the temperature and laminates thickness change of woven-CF/PPS laminates by induction welding in constant of $P=500W$ at 180mm of K-type thermocouple. PPS resin inside the woven-CF/PPS laminates expanded by induction heating using an induction coil. Therefore, at the peak temperature, the combined thickness of two laminates boards became 3mm or more. From this, it is speculated that the internal pressure is given to the interface of the joining part of the woven-

CF/PPS laminates by the expansion of PPS resin. After that, the combined thickness of the two laminates was pressurized to about 2.6mm by the pressure roller.

Figure 8: Change of temperature and laminates thickness for processing time at 180mm of K-type thermocouple. ($P=500W$)

Figure 9 shows the cross-sectional images of junctions at high frequency powers of $P=500W$ and $P=600W$. The digital microscope (Olympus Co., DSX500) was used to observe the cross-sectional image. The deterioration of the end can be confirmed in any cross-sectional image. This is because the PPS resin was thermally decomposed as a result of being heated by a phenomenon called edge effect. The high frequency power $P=600W$ was confirmed to have many voids compared with $P=500W$. This can be confirmed to be close to $400^{\circ}C$ at a plurality of locations in the surface temperature distribution of woven-CF/PPS laminates shown in Figure 6(c). Since the joining part peak temperature is almost the same as the surface peak temperature, it is thought that gasification of the PPS resin occurred due to overheating above the thermal decomposition temperature. Therefore, high frequency power (P) in induction welding of woven-CF/PPS laminates is more than around $500W$ or more and less than $600W$.

Figure 9: Cross-sectional images of joining part by digital microscope.

3.2 SLJ test and fracture surface

As a result of SLJ test, single lap shear strength at $P=500W$ was 16-23MPa. The single lap shear strength of the SLJ specimen was higher at the center than at the edge. Figure 10 shows the fracture surface of the SLJ specimens with single lap shear strength of 23MPa. The digital microscope was used to observe the fracture surface. As can be seen from Figure 10(a), shear failure of PPS resin was confirmed over the entire area of the joining part. Moreover, the crater resulting from shear failure of PPS resin can be confirmed from Figure 10(b). However, it can't be confirm the cutting of carbon fiber at any location. Therefore, it was found that PPS resin on the surface layer of woven-CF/PPS laminates was welding by induction welding in this study.

Figure 10: Fracture surface images observed by microscope. ($P=500W$)

3.3 Deterioration of laminate surface and reverse side

Figure 11 shows the surface and reverse side image of woven-CF/PPS laminates after induction welding at $P=500W$, $q_a=0L/min$ or $50L/min$. It can be seen from Figure 11(a) that the surface of woven-CF/PPS laminates was deteriorated by overheating due to induction heating. There are three main causes of this deterioration. There is oxidation that is linked to oxygen in the air by melting PPS resin at induction heating, transparency caused by crystallinity of PPS resin, and carbonization of woven-CF/PPS laminates by edge effect. On the other hand, no change such as deterioration was seen on the reverse side of woven-CF/PPS laminates. From this, it can be inferred that the induction heating by the MHz band significantly generates surface heating due to the skin effect. Therefore, it is desirable to suppress overheating of woven-CF/PPS laminates surface during induction welding. Various researchers have proposed methods of surface cooling in induction welding [5][11][12][13][14]. We suppressed the overheat using forced air cooling with cooling air volume $q_a=50 L/min$ in this study. As a result, as can be seen from Figure 11(b), it can be seen that the deterioration of woven-CF/PPS laminates was suppressed. However, since it is not possible to suppress edge effects, another approach is necessary for this.

Figure 11: Surface and back side image of woven-CF/PPS laminates. ($P=500W$)

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we investigated the induction welding behavior of woven-CF/PPS laminates using the high frequency power source variable from 1.8 to 2.2MHz. As a result, it was found that the laminates thickness changed with induction heating by the induction coil and pressurization by the pressure roller. In addition, it was also confirmed that PPS resins on the surface of woven-CF/PPS laminates were welded by induction welding from the condition of the fractured surface. The surface of woven-CF/PPS laminates is degraded by induction welding due to various factors. Therefore, degradation was suppressed by performing forced air cooling. However, it was also found that using forced air cooling can't prevent deterioration of the laminates edge due to the edge effect.

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REFERENCES

- [1] T.J. Ahmed, D. Stavrov, H.E.N. Bersee and A. Beukers, *Induction welding of thermoplastic composites - an overview*, Composites: Part A, Vol. 37, 2005, pp. 1638-1651.
- [2] G. Gardiner, *Welding thermoplastic composite*, Composite World, Sep. 9, 2018, pp. 50-63.
- [3] P. Mitschang, and D. Maurer, *Quality controlled induction welding by adapted process parameters*, SAMPE Journal, Vol. 53, No.1, 2017, pp. 42-50.
- [4] V. Rudnev, DLR. Cook, M. Black, *Handbook of induction heating*, 2003.
- [5] R. Rudolf, P. Mitschang, and M. Neitzel, *Induction heating of continuous carbon-fibre-reinforced thermoplastics*, Composites: Part A, Vol. 31, 2000, pp. 1191-1202.
- [6] D. Tanabe, K. Kurauchi, K. Nishiyabu, T. Kurashiki, *Effects of fiber reinforcement pattern on high frequency induction heating behavior of unidirectional and woven CFRTP laminates*, Journal of the Society of Materials Science, Japan, Vol. 65, No. 8, 2016, pp. 611-617.
- [7] M. Muddassir and M. Gurka, *Effect of nickel coated carbon fiber and nickel coated graphite particles on induction heating*, ICCM20, 2015.
- [8] D. Mattheß, D. Landgrebe and W. Drossel, *Inductive heating of glass fibre-reinforced thermoplastics using fibre- and wire-shaped stainless steel susceptors*, Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials, Vol. 30(1), 2015 pp 67-87.
- [9] O. Schieler and U. Beier, *Induction Welding of Hybrid Thermoplastic-thermoset Composite Parts*, KMUTNB Int J Appl Sci Technol, Vol. 9, No. 1, 2016, pp. 27-36.
- [10] J.K. Jackowski, R.C. Goldstein and V.S. Nemkov, *Induction Process and Coil Design for Welding of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics*, SAMPE, 2014.
- [11] K. Kurima, D. Tanabe and K. Nishiyabu, *Evaluation on joining strength of woven CF/PPS laminates bonded by continuous high-frequency induction heating*, ACCM11, 2018.
- [12] M. Duhovic, P. L'Eplattenier, I. Caldichoury, P. Mitschang and M. Maier, *Advanced 3D finite element simulation of thermoplastic carbon fiber composite induction welding*, ECCM16, 2014.
- [13] S. Pappada, A. Salomi, J. Montanaro, A. Passaro, A. Caruso and A. Maffezzoli, *Fabrication of a thermoplastic matrix composite stiffened panel by induction welding*, Aerospace Science and Technology, Vol. 43, 2015, pp. 314-320.
- [14] G. Bernhar and G. Erb, *Investigation of continuous induction welding of C/PAEK laminates*, Aerospace Science and Technology, ECCM18, 2018.